

A RARE CASE OF MULTIPLE FACIAL SEBORRHEIC KERATOSES AND VERRUCA VULGARIS WITH FILIFORM TYPE IN A GERIATRIC PATIENT

Nur Putri Nuzul Iryani*, Khairuddin Djawad*, Siswanto Wahab* and Farida Tabri*,¹

*Department of Dermatology and Venereology Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT

Geriatric is one of the critical age groups in the field of dermatology because some diseases are more common in geriatric patients. One of them is seborrheic keratosis. Verruca vulgaris is commonly found in children and adolescents and is rarely found in patients more than 60 years of age. It is usually found on the dorsal hands and fingers. Clinical features of this disease are hyperkeratotic and dome-shaped papules or nodules.

We report a 64-year-old patient with a chief complaint of verrucous papules and nodules over the face and scalp for almost 20 years which kept on increasing in size and number. The diagnosis was made based on history taking, physical and dermatological examination, dermoscopy, and histopathologic findings. Patients were treated with shave excision and electrocauterization and showed good response.

KEYWORDS common warts, face, geriatric, seborrheic keratosis, verruca vulgaris

Introduction

Geriatric is a particular age group in dermatology due to its high incidence of certain dermatologic and systemic diseases. A study by Kartal et al. described five most common diseases in 7412 geriatric patients, which are eczema (32.2%), followed by infections and skin infestations (18.5%), pruritus (9.5%), benign tumours (9.2%), and erythroscamous disease (5.7%). Among all benign tumours in this study, seborrheic keratosis was the most common benign tumour. [1]

Seborrheic keratosis, also known as seborrheic warts, basal cell papillomas, and senile keratosis, senile warts, is one of the most common skin tumours which mostly affect elderly patients (over 50 years old). [2, 3] The lesions are well-defined, round to oval, slightly elevated, and have a verrucous surface with

predilection on the trunk, head, neck, and extremities. However, it cannot be found on the palms and legs. Diagnosis is usually made clinically, but it is essential to differentiate it from malignant skin tumours. Histopathologically, seborrheic keratosis is characterized by acanthosis, papillomatosis, hyperkeratosis, and horn cysts. Three major histological subtypes are acanthotic, hyperkeratotic, and adenoid seborrheic keratosis. [4]

Warts or verruca vulgaris are benign proliferations of the skin caused by the Human Papilloma Virus (HPV). Verruca Vulgaris can manifest as scaly, firm, verrucous papules or nodules, with a size ranging from less than 1 mm to larger than 1 cm in diameter that can be found on any skin surface but most commonly on the hands, feet, and fingers. This infection can occur at any age and peaks at 12-16 years of age. [8] Diagnosis of verruca is based on physical examination but can be supported by histological features of acanthosis, papillomatosis, hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, elongation of rete ridges and curved towards the central verruca.

In this report, we report a case of multiple facial seborrheic keratoses and verruca vulgaris in a 64-year-old male patient. The diagnosis was based on history taking, physical examination, and dermoscopy

Copyright © 2019 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons

DOI: 10.5455/IJMRCR.multiple-facial-seborrheic-keratoses

First Received: December 17, 2018

Accepted: January 06, 2019

Reviewer: Ivan Inkov (BG);

¹Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University, Jalan Perintis Kemerdekaan Km 10, Makassar, Indonesia.;

farida.tabri.dv@gmail.com

Figure 1. Clinical photograph of multiple, verrucous papules and nodules, some with hyperpigmented papules and plaques on the face present for almost 20 years (A-C).

Figure 2. Dermoscopic features of verruca vulgaris (A) mosaic pattern combined with exophytic keratotic projection pattern with dotted vessels, and seborrheic keratosis (B) circumscribed, brown in colour with a comedo-like opening, and milia-like cyst.

Case Report

A 64-year-old male came to the Department of Dermatology and Venereology, Faculty of Medicine, Hasanuddin University, with a chief complaint of rough brownish nodules over the face and scalp. This complaint began with few rough papules on the right cheek 20 years ago. Also, there were brownish papules over the face. The lesions increased in size and number involving the face and scalp. No treatments were received for this complaint. The similar complaint also affected another member of the family (aunt). He denied the history of atopy, food and drug allergy, and diabetes. Currently, he has retired from his previous job as a seaman.

On physical examination, the general condition was good normal vital signs. Dermatological examination showed multiple, well-defined, verrucous, greyish papules and nodules, measuring 0.5 cm to 1 cm in diameter; multiple, well defined, hyperpigmented papules and plaques, measuring 0.2 cm to 1.5 cm which involved face and scalp.

Dermoscopic examination shows a symmetrical, circumscribed, white-grey papul with exophytic keratotic projection pattern in the left malar region associated with dotted vessel supports the diagnosis of verruca vulgaris. Also, a circumscribed, brown in colour with a comedo-like opening, and milia-like cyst were also be found. This description is consistent with the diagnosis of seborrheic keratosis.

The results of routine blood examination, random blood glucose, and coagulation time were all within normal limit. Shave

Figure 3. The histopathological result showed acanthosis, hyperkeratosis, papillomatosis (A). Koilocytes were found in the granulosum layer (B) with mild infiltration of lymphohistiocytic inflammatory cells in superficial dermis (C).

excision was done in brown lesion over the right temporal dex-tra and greyish nodule over the left cheek. Histopathological examination showed acanthosis, papillomatosis, hyperkeratosis. Some koilocytes were found in the granulosum layer, with mild infiltration of lymphohistiocytic inflammatory cells in the superficial dermis. Other findings were an elongation of rete ridges extends toward the centre. Biopsy results are by the diagnosis of verruca vulgaris.

According to a physical examination, dermoscopic, and the histopathological result, the patient was diagnosed with verruca vulgaris and seborrheic keratosis. The treatment is given after shave excision and electrocauterization was cefadroxil 500 mg b.i.d for ten days, mefenamic acid 500 mg t.i.d, gentamicin ointment, and home wound care. On the seventh day, the wound was dry with no pain. Dermatological examination showed crust with no pus noted. Previous therapy was continued with wound care management.

Discussion

A 64-year-old male patient presented with rough nodules on the face. A study by Gopal et al. found that out of 637 verruca vulgaris in 110 patients, 76 patients were male, and 34 were female. Seborrheic keratosis was mostly found among 18-30 years old age group (76,4%), while ten patients were above 60 years old. [5] Rao et al. conducted a study on 90 patients with verruca vulgaris and found that the incidence in males (74,4%) was significantly higher than female. [6] Chandrashekar et al. also found that 97 men and 47 women had verruca vulgaris. [7] This finding may be related to increased outdoor activity in men and the rising trend of cosmetic concern. [8] Hyperpigmented papules and plaques on the face and scalp were consistent with the diagnosis of seborrheic keratosis. A study by Yeatman et al. in 100 adult patients with seborrheic keratosis, showed 100% of patients belong to 50-year-old age group with total lesions of 69 per patient at the age of more than 75-year-old. [9] Seborrheic keratosis is commonly found on the trunk, especially interscapular, neck, face, and arms. [3] A study by Del Rosso et al. in 406 adult patients with seborrheic keratosis, found that 85% of patients have lesions on the trunk and 68% over the face. [10] Previous studies showed 80.8% verruca measuring ≤ 0.5 cm and as much as 86.4% measuring 0.6-1 cm. [5] Verruca Vulgaris appeared as multiple, papules or nodules, rough and horned surface with varying sizes, ranging from <1 mm to >1 cm.[11-14] It is most often found on the back of the hands and fingers, but it can occur anywhere on the skin. [15] Solitary verruca vulgaris can last unchanged for several months or several years, but some lesions can enlarge quickly or gradually after a few years. Verruca vulgaris is usually asymptomatic. [14] A study by Gopal et al. found the clinical manifestation of verruca vulgaris as dome-shaped papules or plaques with rough surfaces

and blackish brown pigmentation. [5] Filiform type of verrucae formed pedunculated and speculations that grew perpendicular or tilted to the skin surface. It usually found over the face and neck as solitary or multiple lesions. Filiform warts are one of the morphological variations of verruca vulgaris that caused by HPV type 2.[16]

Dermoscopic examination of the verrucous lesion showed a symmetrical, circumscribed, white-grey papule with exophytic keratotic projection pattern on the left malar area associated with the dotted vessel. This result was similar with previously published dermoscopic features of verruca vulgaris that showed frogspawn pattern, mosaic pattern, and either linear, dotted, hairpin, coiled vessels. [17, 18] Most of the verruca has a mosaic pattern followed by a projection pattern of exophytic keratotic. Li et al. found an exophytic keratotic projection pattern, daisy flower patterns, and blood vessels resembling hairpins. [19]

Dermoscopic examination of seborrheic keratosis showed a circumscribed, brown in colour with a comedo-like opening, and milia-like cyst. Dermoscopy is a useful tool to confirm the diagnosis of seborrheic keratosis. Rajesh et al. evaluated 250 cases with seborrheic keratosis with various clinical manifestations and found a comedo-like opening (80%), fissures and ridges (52%), and well-defined border (82.6%). Other less frequent features are the moth-eaten border, milia-like cyst, and network-like structure. [20]

Histopathological examination showed acanthosis, papillomatosis, hyperkeratosis. Some coilocytes were found in the granulosum layer, with mild infiltration of lymphohistiocytic inflammatory cells in the superficial dermis. Other findings were an elongation of rete ridges extends toward the centre. Biopsy results are by the diagnosis of verruca vulgaris. Histopathological features of verruca showed acanthosis, papillomatosis, hyperkeratosis, parakeratosis, elongation of rete ridges and curved towards the central verruca. Capillary blood vessels are more prominent and thrombosis. Also, there are also large keratinocytes with an eccentric pycnotic nucleus surrounded by a perinuclear halo (koilocytes) characteristic of HPV-related papillomas. [21]

Histopathological features of seborrheic keratosis are almost the same as verruca vulgaris, including hyperkeratosis, acanthosis, and papillomatosis. Also, horn cyst and squamous eddies can also be found. [2] In this patient, a biopsy was performed on the suspected lesion of seborrheic keratosis, but the histopathological features more of verruca vulgaris. Dermoscopy examination consistent with seborrheic keratosis and there were no signs of malignancy.

Papules and nodules have appeared for 20 years with no sign of spontaneous regression. Spontaneous regression of verruca vulgaris can occur, and sometimes it did not require therapy. Verruca of long duration and in immunosuppressed patients are less likely to experience spontaneous resolution and more recalcitrant to therapy. [21, 22]

Electrocauterization and curettage destructive therapy have been widely used. The success rate of this method is reported to be 65-85%. Scarring usually occurs after the surgery and the recurrence rate is almost 30%. This destructive therapy is intended to damage or eliminate lesions, not to kill the virus. Some forms of this destructive therapy include curettage, chemical cautery, and cryotherapy to hyperthermic therapy. [21]

Shave biopsy is most often used because it is quick and inexpensive with a cosmetically satisfying result. Superficial shave biopsy is used for lesions found mainly in the epidermal layer

without expansion to the dermis, such as verruca, papillomas, skin tags, and seborrheic/actinic keratosis. This biopsy will remove the epidermis and upper dermis (less than 1 mm) using scalpel number 15. [23]

In the seborrheic keratosis lesions, electrocauterization was performed. Therapeutic options for patients with seborrheic keratosis include curettage, electrodesiccation, cryotherapy, and ablative laser. [2] Electrocautery is simple, inexpensive, and has been widely used in the field of dermatology with the same cosmetic results as CO2 lasers. [24]

Disclosure Statement

There were no financial support or relationships between the authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interests.

Competing Interests

Written informed consent obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images.

References

1. Kartal D, Çınar SL, Akın S, Ferahbaş A, Borlu M. Skin findings of geriatric patients in Turkey: A 5-year survey. *Dermatologica Sinica*. 2015;33(4):196-200.
2. Hafner C, Vogt T. Seborrheic keratosis. *Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft = Journal of the German Society of Dermatology: JDDG*. 2008;6(8):664-77.
3. Rajabi P, Adibi N, Nematollahi P, Heidarpour M, Eftekhari M, Siadat AH. Bowenoid transformation in seborrheic keratosis: A retrospective analysis of 429 patients. *Journal of research in medical sciences: the official journal of Isfahan University of Medical Sciences*. 2012;17(3):217-21.
4. Zhang R-z, Zhu W-y. Seborrheic keratoses in five elderly patients: An appearance of raindrops and streams. *Indian journal of dermatology*. 2011;56(4):432.
5. Gopal V, Shenoy MM, Pinto M. Common warts revisited: a clinical study. *International Journal of Research in Dermatology*. 2017;3(2):261-6.
6. Sudhakar Rao K, Ankad B, Naidu V, Sampaghavi V, Vinod AM. A clinical study on warts. *Journal of Clinical and Diagnostic Research*. 2011;5(8):1582-4.
7. Chandrashekar L. Viral warts-A clinico-epidemiological study. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*. 2003;48(3):142-5.
8. Ghadgepatil SS, Gupta S, Sharma YK. Clinicoepidemiological study of different types of warts. *Dermatology research and practice*. 2016;2016.
9. Yeatman J, Kilkenny M, Marks R. The prevalence of seborrheic keratoses in an Australian population: does exposure to sunlight play a part in their frequency? *British Journal of Dermatology*. 1997;137(3):411-4.
10. Del Rosso JQ. A Closer Look at Seborrheic Keratoses: Patient Perspectives, Clinical Relevance, Medical Necessity, and Implications for Management. *The Journal of clinical and aesthetic dermatology*. 2017;10(3):16-25.

11. Androphy E, Kirnbauer R. Human Papilloma Virus Infections. In: Goldsmith L, Katz S, Gilchrist B, Paller A, Leffell D, Wolff K, editors. *Fitzpatrick's Dermatology in General Medicine*. 8th ed. New York: Mc.Graw Hill Medical; 2012. p. 2421-33.
12. Cipto H. *Veruka Vulgaris dan Veruka Plana. Ilmu Penyakit Kulit dan Kelamin*. 7th ed. Jakarta: Fakultas Kedokteran Universitas Indonesia; 2016. p. 131.
13. Paul H. Generalized Verruca Vulgaris: A case reports. *Dhaka Community Med Coll Journal*. 2017;6(1):29-32.
14. Murlistyarini S, Prawitasari S, Setyowatie L. *Intisari Ilmu Kesehatan Kulit dan Kelamin: Universitas Brawijaya Press*; 2018.
15. Sterling J. Viral Infections. In: Burns T, Brethnach S, Cox N, Griffiths C, editors. *Rooks Textbook of Dermatology*. 8th ed. West Sussex: Willey Blackwell; 2010. p. 33-59.
16. Sterling J. Viral Infections. In: Burns T, Breathnach S, Cox N, Griffiyyths C, editors. *Textbook of Dermatology*. 7th ed. Oxford: Blackwell Science; 2004. p. 25, 37-60.
17. Zalaudek I, Giacomel J, Cabo H, Di Stefani A, Ferrara G, Hofmann-Wellenhof R, et al. Entodermoscopy: a new tool for diagnosing skin infections and infestations. *Dermatology*. 2008;216(1):14-23.
18. Yoong C, Di Stefani A, Hofmann-Wellenhof R, Campbell T, Soyer HP. Unusual clinical and dermoscopic presentation of a wart. *Australasian Journal of Dermatology*. 2009;50(3):228-9.
19. Li X, Yu J, Thomas S, Lee K, Soyer HP. Clinical and dermoscopic features of common warts. *Journal of the European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology*. 2017;31(7):e308-e10.
20. Rajesh G, Thappa DM, Jaisankar TJ, Chandrashekar L. Spectrum of seborrheic keratoses in South Indians: a clinical and dermoscopic study. *Indian journal of dermatology, venereology and leprology*. 2011;77(4):483-8.
21. Sterling J, Handfield-Jones S, Hudson P. Guidelines for the management of cutaneous warts. *British Journal of Dermatology*. 2001;144(1):4-11.
22. Berth-Jones J, Hutchinson P. Modern treatment of warts: cure rates at 3 and 6 months. *British Journal of Dermatology*. 1992;127(3):262-5.
23. Pickett H. Shave and punch biopsy for skin lesions. *American family physician*. 2011;84(9):995.
24. M.M. Ali B, El-Tatawy RA, Ismael MA, Gawdat AM. Electrocautery versus ablative CO2 laser in the treatment of seborrheic keratoses: a clinical and histopathological study. *Journal of the Egyptian Women's Dermatologic Society*. 2014;11(2):136-41.